

Stabilization of manganese(III) in aqueous medium. Synthesis and spectral characterization of new mixed-ligand fluoromanganate(III) containing dicarboxylic and hydroxy-carboxylic acids as co-ligands

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Manuscript received 06 October 2010, revised 05 May 2011, accepted 20 June 2011

Abstract : Fluoride assisted stabilization of manganese(III) has been demonstrated by synthesizing new mixed-ligand fluoromanganate(III) complexes from aqueous medium. Mixed-ligand fluoromanganate(III) complexes have been synthesized from a reaction of $MnO(OH)$, 40% HF with corresponding co-ligands in aqueous medium in presence of alkali metal carbonate. Newly synthesized complexes are stable in absence of moisture and are insoluble in organic solvents. Complexes were characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, chemical determination of oxidation state, FTIR, electronic spectra, room temperature magnetic moment measurements, TGA/DTA, SEM, EDX and cyclic voltammetry studies. The synthesized complexes are likely to have distorted octahedral structure.

Keywords : Stabilization, manganese(III), aqueous medium.

Introduction

Manganese can exist in a number of oxidation states, and this ability of manganese probably accounts for the metal being present at the active sites of several redox enzymes¹⁻³. The tri-positive state of manganese requires special attention, not only due to its biochemical relevance in diverse redox functions¹⁻³, but also due to the fact that it is difficult to stabilize Mn(III) in aqueous medium⁴. Several manganese(III) complexes exhibit unusual magnetic and structural features^{5,7} and stable manganese(III) building blocks can be used as a precursor of single molecule magnets⁸. Coordination chemistry of manganese(III) is, however, not easy to explore because of its fairly oxidizing power and its ability to undergo disproportionation in aqueous medium. Thus the isolation of stable solid manganese(III) complexes is rather difficult to achieve. However, it is expected that complex formation⁹ would lead to lowering of the reduction potential of Mn(III)/Mn(II) couple thereby stabilizing manganese(III). Thus, selection of appropriate ligands and suitable routes for the synthesis of stable manganese(III) complexes from aqueous solution is an important pre-requisites for further studies.

There have been indications in regard of capability

of fluoride ion, hydroxy acids especially α -hydroxy acids and dicarboxylic acids in stabilizing manganese(III) ion in solution^{4,7,10}. Strong basic ligand like fluoride has a pronounced stabilizing effect on manganese(III) both in solution as well as in solid state, and coordination of fluoride also introduces antiferromagnetism in the fluoromanganate(III) compounds^{5,7}. The chemistry of mixed-ligand fluoromanganates(III) is expected to be interesting and significant since the concept of addition of ligands changes the property¹¹ as compared to those of the corresponding binary complexes.

Biogenic ligands like α -hydroxy acids serve as important substrate in many biochemical processes¹². However, reports on mixed-ligand fluoromanganate(III) complexes containing biogenic co-ligands are rather sparse¹³. Similarly, the coordination chemistry of dicarboxylic acids is less explored¹⁴ and report on fluoro-dicarboxylic acid-manganese(III) complexes are not known to best of our knowledge. As mentioned (*vide-infra*), hydroxy acids and dicarboxylic acid might stabilize the manganese(III) oxidation level, but there is little literature evidence based on structurally well defined and chemically characterized manganese(III) complexes containing these groups to evaluate this idea. In line with our contention, it was expected

that an introduction of F⁻ ligand would be able to contribute significantly towards stabilizing Mn(III)- α -hydroxy acid and Mn(III)-dicarboxylic acid systems, leading to an access to mixed-ligand fluoro manganese(III) complexes containing α -hydroxy acid or dicarboxylic acid as co-ligand. As a case in point, therefore, it appears to be fruitful to explore the chemistry of mixed-ligand fluoromanganese(III) containing biogenic co-ligands, viz. α -hydroxy acids and dicarboxylic acids, to gather more knowledge in the field of manganese(III) chemistry.

Accordingly, synthetic strategies were chalked out for obtaining hitherto unknown mixed-ligand fluoro manganese(III) complexes containing α -hydroxymonocarboxylic acid, α -hydroxydicarboxylic acid and simple dicarboxylic acid as co-ligands from aqueous medium. Co-ligands chosen for the present investigation were lactic, malic and malonic acids respectively. The work presented herein, deals with synthesis, spectral characterization and an assessment of structure of new mixed-ligand fluoromanganate(III) compounds containing biogenic co-ligands.

Experimental

Materials :

The chemicals used were all reagent grade products. The compound MnO(OH) was prepared by the oxidation of Mn(OH)₂ with H₂O₂¹⁵.

Synthesis of mixed-ligand fluoromanganate(III) of the type A₂[MnF₄(L)] (L = lactate or malate, A = Na, K, NH₄) and A₃[MnF₄(L)].H₂O (L = malonate, A = Na, K, NH₄) :

General procedure :

An amount of 0.89 g (10.11 mmol) of freshly prepared MnO(OH) was dissolved in 2.0 mL (40.00 mmol) of 40% HF with continuous stirring. The solution was then stirred for *ca.* 10 min followed by the addition of 1.0 mL of lactic acid (13.42 mmol)/1.355 g (10.11 mmol) malic acid/1.052 g (10.11 mmol) malonic acid, and the resultant solution was stirred for a further period of *ca.* 15 min. To the resulting mixture a specific amount of A₂CO₃ (A = Na, K, NH₄) was added with stirring keeping the MnO(OH) : A₂CO₃ ratio as 1 : 1, followed by slow addition of pre-cooled acetone whereupon pink microcrystalline product precipitated out. The compounds were col-

lected by filtration, washed three to four times with small volume of acetone and dried *in vacuo* over conc. H₂SO₄.

Several attempts for obtaining single crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction study were not successful.

Physical measurements :

IR spectra were recorded on a BOMEMDA-8 Perkin-Elmer Spectrum 100, FTIR spectrometer. Electronic spectra were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer model Lambda-25 spectrophotometer. The Gouy method was used to measure the magnetic susceptibility of the complexes with Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as the standard. TGA/DTA study was carried out using Perkin-Elmer Pyris diamond model at the heating rate of 5 °C /min under N₂ atmosphere. The SEM characterization was carried out by using the LEO1430VP Scanning Electron Micrograph attached with energy dispersive X-ray detector. Scanning was done at 10–50 μ M range and images were taken at a magnification of 15–20 kV. Cyclic voltammetric studies were performed using Electrochemical Analyser instrument model CH620A with glassy carbon working electrode, a platinum counter electrode and Ag/AgCl standard electrode with 10⁻³ M solution of KCl as supporting electrolyte.

Elemental analyses :

Manganese was estimated volumetrically by complexometric titration with EDTA^{16a} using Erio-T as indicator. The fluoride contents of the compounds were determined by Volhard's method^{16b}. Sodium, potassium were determined by the method reported in literature¹⁷. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were estimated by micro-analytical methods (Analytical data are given in Table 1).

Chemical determination of the oxidation state of manganese :

The oxidation state of manganese was determined iodometrically by treating a freshly prepared ice-cold potassium iodide solution, acidified with dilute sulfuric acid, with the compound followed by titration of the liberated iodine against a standard sodium thiosulfate solution. The iodometric experiment was done under ice-cold condition.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The problem associated with the synthesis of

Table 1. Analytical data for the complexes

Compd.	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
		A or N	Mn	F	C	H
K ₂ [MnF ₄ (L)]	79	26.09 (26.17)	18.50 (18.45)	25.52 (25.50)	12.06 (12.08)	1.64 (1.68)
Na ₂ [MnF ₄ (L)]	73	17.21 (17.29)	20.69 (20.68)	28.55 (28.57)	13.51 (13.53)	1.85 (1.88)
(NH ₄) ₂ [MnF ₄ (L)] (L = lactate)	78	10.92 (10.94)	21.49 (21.48)	29.71 (29.69)	14.04 (14.06)	1.94 (1.95)
K ₂ [MnF ₄ (L)]	81	22.79 (22.81)	16.09 (16.08)	22.24 (22.22)	14.05 (14.04)	1.43 (1.46)
Na ₂ [MnF ₄ (L)] (L = malate)	74	14.82 (14.84)	17.75 (17.74)	24.53 (24.52)	15.47 (15.48)	1.62 (1.61)
K ₃ [MnF ₄ (L)].H ₂ O	82	31.78 (31.79)	14.97 (14.95)	20.67 (20.65)	9.76 (9.78)	1.07 (1.09)
Na ₃ [MnF ₄ (L)].H ₂ O	70	21.54 (21.56)	17.20 (17.19)	23.74 (23.75)	11.26 (11.25)	1.27 (1.25)
(NH ₄) ₃ [MnF ₄ (L)].H ₂ O (L = malonate)	76	13.75 (13.77)	18.05 (18.03)	24.95 (24.92)	11.81 (11.80)	5.28 (5.25)

manganese(III) compounds from aqueous medium is the tendency of the metal ion to disproportionate to manganese(IV) and manganese(II)⁴. In view of the pronounced stabilizing effect of fluoride ion on manganese(III), it was anticipated that the problem associated with synthesis of manganese(III) complexes from aqueous medium may be encountered by carrying out the reaction in an acidic medium in presence of fluoride ion. It was expected that this strategy would lead to synthesis of stable mixed-ligand fluoro complexes of manganese(III) from aqueous medium. The reaction of MnO(OH) in 40% HF with the corresponding co-ligand (lactic, malic or malonic acid) in presence of A₂CO₃ (A = Na, K, NH₄) were performed and addition of acetone afforded the micro-crystalline products. Similar reactions at higher pH gave products which were impure in nature. Alkali metal and ammonium carbonates acted as the source of cation.

Thus it is evident from the foregoing discussion that fluoride ion has assisted in the stabilization of manganese(III) in aqueous solution in presence of different co-ligands and allowed isolation of stable new mixed-ligand fluoromanganate(III) complexes containing biogenic co-ligands from aqueous medium.

Characterization and assessment of structure :

The newly synthesized complexes were characterized

and an assessment of their structures were made on the basis of elemental analyses, chemical determination of oxidation state, FTIR, electronic spectroscopy, room temperature magnetic moment measurements, TGA/DTA, SEM, EDX and electrochemical studies. Elemental analyses of the compounds agree well with the proposed formulation of the complexes. All the newly synthesized compounds are stable in the absence of moisture and can be stored for a prolonged periods in sealed polythene bags. The stability of the compounds can be ascertained by periodic estimation of manganese and fluoride content and also by recording of their infrared spectra. The compounds undergo slow decomposition in water, however, malonate complexes are relatively more stable in aqueous solution in comparison to others. All the newly synthesized compounds are practically insoluble in common organic solvents.

Chemical determination of the oxidation state :

Importance of the chemical determination of oxidation state of manganese is emphasized because many manganese(III) compounds show anomalous magnetic behavior^{6,7}, leading to confusion regarding the actual oxidation state of the metal. The chemically estimated oxidation state of the metal in the newly synthesized complexes were found to lie between 3.0 to 3.1, suggesting

that manganese occur in its +3 oxidation state in each of the compound.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the synthesized complexes exhibit similar features in terms of their position, pattern and intensities of the observed bands (Table 2). The electronic spectra of freshly prepared complexes were recorded immediately after making an aqueous solution containing very small amount of HF. In case of lactate and malate complexes bands were observed at *ca.* 23866 cm^{-1} , *ca.* 19120–18348 cm^{-1} and *ca.* 13830 cm^{-1} . The observed bands were assigned to ${}^5B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$, ${}^5B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^5B_{2g}$ and ${}^5B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^5A_{1g}$ modes of transitions respectively¹⁸. Absorptions for malonate complexes were observed at *ca.* 18181 cm^{-1} and *ca.* 12500 cm^{-1} and were assigned as ${}^5B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^5B_{2g}$ and ${}^5B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^5A_{1g}$ modes of transitions respectively. The observed spectral pattern is characteristic of the presence of high spin manganese(III) ion and suggest an appreciable splitting of 5E_g ground state of manganese(III) leading to a distorted octahedral environment around manganese(III) centre¹⁹ in the complex species. Appearance of an intense band in the region 225–235 nm (42000–44000 cm^{-1}) in all the compounds may be attributed to charge-transfer transition¹⁸.

Magnetic measurements :

The room temperature (300 K) magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes show magnetic moment values for $A_2[MnF_4(L)]$ (L = lactate, malate) to lie in the range of 4.9–5.1 μ_B , while those of $A_3[MnF_4(L)] \cdot H_2O$ (L = malonate) exhibit magnetic moment values between 4.7–4.8 μ_B (Table 2). These values are normal as expected for a high spin d^4 system of manganese(III) ion and show that the strong anti ferromagnetism usually encountered in binary fluoromanganates(III) $[MnF_5]^{2-}$ ^{6,7} is rather practically absent in case of the newly synthesized mixed-ligand complexes. The observed magnetic moment values and electronic spectral band positions unequivocally suggest the presence of high spin manganese(III) ion in each of the newly synthesized complexes reported herein.

Infrared spectra :

Infrared spectra of the complexes displayed sufficiently well resolved spectral pattern, significant features of which

are summarized in Table 3. The notable features of the infrared spectra of the complex containing lactate as co-ligand, $A_2[MnF_4(L)]$ (A = Na, K, NH_4 , L = lactate), involve absorptions due to coordinated lactate and fluoride ligands. The mode of coordination of lactate ion can be ascertained from a consideration of IR spectra of the compound and comparing them with the spectra of the free acid. Free acid exhibit broad absorption band in the region 3550 cm^{-1} due to -OH stretching frequency and a band at *ca.* 1710 cm^{-1} is attributable to $\nu(C=O)$ of undissociated -COOH group²⁰.

Carboxylate ion can coordinate to a metal center in a variety of way. The difference between $[\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{COO}) - \nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO})]$, $\Delta\nu$, value of carboxylate group allows one to distinguish among the unidentate, chelating bidentate and bridging mode of coordination of the carboxylate group. Separation significantly less than that of ionic value ($\sim 164 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is indicative of chelating or bridging carboxylate group, whereas separation substantially greater than the ionic mode is indicative of monodentate coordination²¹. The notable features of the IR spectra of lactate complexes were absorptions observed at *ca.* 1630–1658 cm^{-1} and at *ca.* 1350–1385 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO})$ modes of vibrations of carboxylate group respectively. Absence of any band in the region 1700 cm^{-1} in the complexes attributable to free -COOH group, indicate deprotonation of the carboxylic group. The large value of separation between $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO})$ ($\Delta\nu > 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is typical of monodentate coordination of carboxylate group²¹. Appearance of a sharp band at *ca.* 780 cm^{-1} assigned as $\delta(\text{COO})$. Observance of a medium intensity band at *ca.* 485 cm^{-1} is assignable to $\nu(\text{Mn-O})$ mode of vibration. The terminal mode of coordination of fluoride ligand was ascertained from the appearance of strong bands at *ca.* 583 cm^{-1} and 585 cm^{-1} , attributed to $\nu(\text{Mn-F})$ ²². The lowering of $\nu(\text{OH})$ in complexes in comparison to that of the free acid, observed at *ca.* 3460 cm^{-1} , suggest participation of -OH group in coordination.

FTIR spectra of fluoromalatomanganate(III) complexes, $A_2[MnF_4(L)]$ (L = malate), display characteristic features of the coordinated malato ligand. Strong absorption for antisymmetric stretching carboxylate vibration $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-)$ at 1600–1628 cm^{-1} and the corresponding symmetric stretching vibration $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-)$ appear at *ca.* 1394 cm^{-1} respectively. The difference of frequency between these two modes, $\Delta\nu [\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO}) - \nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO})]$, greater

Table 2. Magnetic moment values and electronic spectral data for the complexes

Compd.	Magnetic moment value at 300 K (μ_B)	Electronic spectral band positions (cm^{-1})		
		${}^5B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^5A_{1g}$ (log ϵ)	${}^5A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^5B_{2g}$ (log ϵ)	${}^5B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ (log ϵ)
$A_2[MnF_4(L)]$ (A = Na, K, NH_4 , L = lactate)	4.9-5.0	11950 (2.204)	18348 (2.342)	23866 (2.543)
$A_2[MnF_4(L)]$ (A = Na, K, NH_4 , L = malate)	5.0-5.1	12280 (2.079)	19120 (2.301)	23250 (2.544)
$A_3[MnF_4(L)].H_2O$ (A = Na, K, NH_4 , L = malonate)	4.7-4.8	12500 (2.053)	18181 (2.398)	-

Table 3. Structurally significant IR bands for the complexes

Compd.	Band position (cm^{-1})	Assignment
$A_2[MnF_4(L)]$ (L = lactate, A = Na, K, NH_4)	3459-3464	$\nu(OH)$
	1630-1658	$\nu_{asy}(COO^-)$
	1350-1380	$\nu_{sym}(COO^-)$
	740-780	$\delta(OCO)$
	583	$\nu(Mn-F)$
	585	
	485	$\nu(Mn-O)$
	3040	$\left. \begin{matrix} \nu_3 \\ \nu_1 \\ \nu_2 \end{matrix} \right\} NH_4^+$
	3160	
	1420-1430	
$A_2[MnF_4(L)]$ (L = malate, A = Na, K)	3430-3464	$\nu(OH)$
	1710-1730	$\nu(COOH)$
	1600-1630	$\nu_{asy}(COO^-)$
	~ 1394	$\nu_{sym}(COO^-)$
	740-780	$\delta(OCO)$
	610	$\nu(Mn-F)$
	615	
~ 480	$\nu(Mn-O)$	
$A_3[MnF_4(L)].H_2O$ (L = malonate, A = Na, K, NH_4)	~ 3440	$\nu(OH)$
	1630-1640	$\nu_{asy}(COO^-)$
	1350-1380	$\nu_{sym}(COO^-)$
	684-744	$\delta(OCO)$
	591	$\nu(Mn-F)$
	615	
	483-486	$\nu(Mn-O)$
	~ 3050	$\left. \begin{matrix} \nu_3 \\ \nu_1 \\ \nu_2 \end{matrix} \right\} NH_4^+$
	~ 3160	
	~ 1410	

than 200 cm^{-1} indicate that COO^- group is coordinated to the metal center in an unidentate fashion²¹. In addition to the above observed bands appearance of a absorption band at *ca.* 1710 cm^{-1} in the complexes is assignable to $\nu(COOH)$ and suggest that an uncoordinated, undissociated terminal carboxylic group exist in the complexes. Observance of a broad band at $3430-3464 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (s, br) was assigned as $\nu(OH)$. The lowering of O-H stretching frequency in the complexes in comparison to that observed for free acid indicate that the hydroxy group is coordinated to the metal center. Such mode of coordination of malic acid is not unprecedented in literature²³. Existence of a medium intensity band at *ca.* 610 cm^{-1} and a shoulder at 615 cm^{-1} confirm the terminal mode of coordination of fluoride. Additional bands at *ca.* $740-780 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 480 cm^{-1} are assignable to $\delta(COO)$ and $\nu(Mn-O)$ modes of vibrations respectively.

The significant features of the IR spectral data for malonate complexes are absorptions due to $\nu_{asy}(COO)$, $\nu_{sym}(COO)$, $\nu(Mn-F)$ and $\nu(Mn-O)$ modes of vibrations, observed in the region $1630-1640$, $1350-1380$, $591-615$ and $483-486 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. Here again, the difference between antisymmetric and symmetric (COO^-) stretching frequency, $\Delta\nu$, greater than 200 cm^{-1} and absence of any band at *ca.* 1700 cm^{-1} due to free carboxylic group ($-COOH$) indicate monodentate coordination of each the carboxylate group and overall bidentate coordination of malonate ion towards the manganese(III) ion. Such mode of coordination of malonate ion is well documented in literature²⁴. The band observed between $591-615 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been assigned to $\nu(Mn-F)$ mode of coordi-

nated fluoride ligand. Additional band at *ca.* 3440 cm^{-1} in case of malonato complexes has been assigned to -OH stretching frequency, $\nu(\text{O-H})$, and resemble in its shape and position to that of lattice water²⁵. The broad nature of -OH stretching band may be attributed to the internal hydrogen bonding between -COO groups and molecule of lattice water present in the complexes. The extra bands in the region 3040–3160 cm^{-1} and at *ca.* 1420 cm^{-1} in case of the ammonium salts of lactate and malonate complexes have been assigned as ν_3 , ν_1 and ν_2 modes of NH_4^+ .

Thermogravimetric studies :

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA/DTA) of lactate complex, $\text{K}_2[\text{MnF}_4(\text{L})]$ (L = lactate) was carried out in the temperature range of 40–1000 °C under nitrogen atmosphere (Fig. 1). The compound undergoes decomposition in the temperature ranges of 90–180 °C, 180–470 °C

and 480–767 °C. Endothermic processes were observed with the corresponding weight loss of 3.5, 3.8 and 6.2% respectively per formula weight of the compound. Observance of endothermic peaks at 180 °C ($\sim 6 \mu\text{V}$) and at 767 °C ($\sim 37 \mu\text{V}$) in DTA curve also lend support to the above decomposition processes. The first two stages of decomposition are attributable to fragmentation of the organic ligand, whereas the later one is due to loss of HF molecule. The origin of HF may be attributed to the abstraction of hydrogen atom from the hydroxy acid ligand. Above 700 °C the complex undergo continuous loss in weight. Thermogravimetric data of the compound agrees well with the formulation of the compound .

SEM and energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) :

SEM (Fig. 2) data show that surface layers of lactate(a) and malonate(c) complexes are having almost similar morphology, however, morphological features of the malate(b)

Fig. 1. TGA/DTA curve for $\text{K}_2[\text{MnF}_4(\text{L})]$ (L = lactate).

Fig. 2. Scanning electron micrograph of (a) $K_2[MnF_4(L)]$ ($L = \text{lactate}$), (b) $K_2[MnF_4(L)]$ ($L = \text{malate}$) and (c) $Na_3[MnF_4(L)] \cdot H_2O$ ($L = \text{malonate}$).

complexes are different from those of the other two complexes reported herein. SEM data show that the surface layers of the malate complexes are homogeneous, whereas those of lactate and malonate complexes are partially homogeneous in nature.

Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy of the compounds, which provides *in situ* chemical analysis of the bulk, clearly showed Mn, F, C, O, K, Na etc. as the

constituent elements of the newly synthesized complexes (Fig. 3). Moreover, the EDX spectral data obtained on the composition of the compounds were in good agreement with the elemental analyses values.

Electrochemical study :

Electrochemical study of complexes, $Na_3[MnF_4(L)] \cdot H_2O$ and $(NH_4)_3[MnF_4(L)] \cdot H_2O$ ($L = \text{malonate}$) were carried

Fig. 3. EDX spectra of (a) $K_2[MnF_4(L)]$ (L = lactate), (b) $K_2[MnF_4(L)]$ (L = malate) and (c) $Na_3[MnF_4(L)].H_2O$ (L = malonate).

out at room temperature by cyclic voltammetry in an aqueous solution (Fig. 4). The sodium salt of complex exhibit a quasi-reversible behavior assignable to Mn(III)/Mn(II) couple with the following characteristics : $E_o = 1.0$ V (vs Ag/AgCl electrode), $E_p = 2.11$ V at a scan rate of 0.2 V s^{-1} with glassy carbon working electrode whereas the

ammonium salt shows one irreversible reduction peak at $+0.6$ V with no corresponding anodic peak.

Thus on the basis of chemical analyses in conjunction with spectral studies the following probable molecular structures are proposed for the newly synthesized complexes (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammogram of (a) $\text{Na}_3[\text{MnF}_4(\text{L})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and (b) $(\text{NH}_4)_3[\text{MnF}_4(\text{L})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (L = malonate).

Fig. 5. Proposed structures for the complexes.

Conclusion :

Stabilization of manganese(III) has been demonstrated by synthesizing a number of mixed-ligand fluoromanganate(III) complexes from aqueous medium. The co-ligands chosen for the synthesis were from α -hydroxy monocarboxylic, α -hydroxy dicarboxylic and dicarboxylic acids viz. lactic, malic, and malonic acid respectively. The significance of chemical determination of the oxidation state of the metal in such compounds has been emphasized. A comparison of the magnetic property of binary fluoromanganate(III) complexes with those of the newly synthesized mixed-ligand fluoromanganate(III) complexes suggest that the strong antiferromagnetism encountered in the binary $[\text{MnF}_5]^{2-}$ complexes^{6,7} is practically absent in case of the newly synthesized compounds. The room temperature magnetic moment values for the complexes are normal as expected for a high spin d^4 system. The electronic spectral study suggests an appreciable splitting of 5E_g ground state of Mn(III) in the complexes. Each of the newly synthesized complexes very likely has a distorted octahedral structure.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance from UGC, New Delhi vide sanction no. F. No. 34/331/2008 (SR) dated 26.12.08 is gratefully acknowledged. The authors are thankful to Professor A. T. Khan, Department of Chemistry, IIT, Guwahati for his cooperation in carrying out magnetic susceptibility measurements. Authors are also thankful to Professor N. S. Islam, Department of Chemistry, Tezpur University for SEM, EDX studies and to Professor M. Bhattacharjee of IIT, Kharagpur for his help and cooperation.

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